

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Assessment of the challenges and prospects of physical planning and rural development in Rivers State, Nigeria

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2022, 16(01), 148–161

Publication history: Received on 30 August 2022; revised on 04 October 2022; accepted on 07 October 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2022.16.1.0998>

Abstract

The study assessed the challenges and prospects of physical planning and rural development in Rivers State, Nigeria. This is vital because it helps in the management of landuses in different rural and urban areas. In achieving these, various objectives were identified including examining the effect of physical planning roles/laws in the development of the areas among others. The sample areas were Abua/Odual, Eleme and Obio/Akpor local government areas with sample size of 399 at 6.5% growth rate. The descriptive statistical tools were used in analyzing the responses. The results from the analysis should that 50% of the respondents are engaged in trading, with highest monthly income of 43.4%. Furthermore, 86.8% are of the respondents are aware of the physical planning authorities in the areas. In conclusion, this study revealed that the presence of physical planning authority but majority refused to take their building plan to the physical planning because of the fees required. The available facilities are police post, borehole, pipe borne water, market, town hall and school. The major provider of the facilities and amenities is the government.

Keywords: Landuse; Challenges; Physical Planning; Prospects; Rural development

1. Introduction

The term planning has been described in several ways as land use planning, town and country planning, urban and regional planning, or simply town planning (Olajuyigbe and Rotowa, 2011). Furthermore, it is defined as the systematic arrangement of land and water, alternative pattern of land use and other physical, social and economic conditions in such a way to encourage land users select options that meets productivity and societal needs in a sustainable manner (Onibokun, 1985). This means that harmonious land uses, warrantieswell-ordered development, providing functional and visually pleasing environment and satisfactory services in a sustainable manner, in other words land is essential for human habitation, be it urban or rural and should bemade to align forsustainability. The assessment of physical planning involves different areas such as land use, socioeconomics, transportation, economic and housing characteristics among others; however, it is a vital factor in the management of rural and urban areas. Ogu and Adeniji (2011) observe that the extent to which human communities both urban and rural, but particularly the urban areas are sustainable may well depend on the management of the settlement. Rural sustainability is directly influenced by land use controls which ensure that efficient use is made of rural land and the acquisition and development of land is the basis of physical growth. The argument on physical planning has brought to the fore the question of physical and socioeconomic development in rural areas as majority of the rural areas fall under customary land. Closely tied to this debate are the issues of planning and the role it plays in ensuring poverty eradication and sustainable rural development. Poverty is most predominant in rural areas as there are no or insufficient infrastructure to cater for the people living in the area. Diangamo, (2013), asserts that the poor makes up around 70% of thetotal population and 80%

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of its rural population in Nigeria. This is a pathetic situation when compared to other African countries like Ghana with poverty rate of 11.3%, Sasu, (2021) and rural population of 43.3% (World Bank, 2019). The result of untold poverty levels in rural areas has been attributed to various factors such as migration of rural dwellers to urban areas with the hope of employment and general better life which has created multiple effects both on the urbanities and ruralites. The rural areas are characterized with poor quality housing, inadequate or lack of health facilities, few schools, poor functioning markets poor road and transport networks. Considering that setting up of the necessary infrastructure, needs financial, physical as well as human resources is the man's quest for socio-economic development and better quality of life, however the conditions of obtaining these in Nigeria, especially in the rural areas, for sustainable development are to a large extent lacking (Mukalula, 2010). This describes the condition of most rural communities in Rivers State and Nigeria as a whole. Rural areas in Nigeria, over the years, have been observed to have suffered from utter neglect and exhibit what has been aptly described as 3Ds namely: depression, degradation and deprivation (Mabogunje, 2014). The colonial administrators consistently adopted a nonchalant, yet unfair attitude towards rural development through neglect, through small budget allocation to rural sector and through failure to provide rural amenities and facilities (Falade, 2011). Viewed against the background of the fact that rural areas in Nigeria provides jobs for over 70% of the population and accounted for 84% of the Nation's GDP at independence and about 60% as at 1965, the neglect suffered by the rural areas is pathetic and inexcusable. The process of rural development is one that has been given some priority by governments at all levels - Federal, State and Local - in Nigeria especially from the early 1970s when increased public revenue from crude oil enabled the government to increase public spending substantially. , the various problems facing the residents of these local government area are; Lack of social amenities, infrastructures are not extended to certain regions, unemployment and Poor road constructions etc.

The need for the development of the rural regions is very important, though in Nigeria, there is no regional development policy, the regional structure of Nigeria is an important factor in everyday decisions of the government and citizens (Mabogunje, 2006). The system of government is the result of regional differences, which are rooted in geographical and historical facts and are moulded by economic, social and cultural forces, regional problems and disparities are the preoccupation of these levels of government (Oyewale, 2014). The causes and effects of regional disequilibrium constitute an important area of study - for example, unemployment, growth-rates, income, migration and rural development. This research seeks to examine physical planning and Rural development in Rivers State, Many studies have been carried out on physical planning and Rural development but non to the best knowledge have been done in rural areas of Eleme, Abua/Odual and Obio/akpor L.G.A in Rivers State.

2. Materials and Methods

Rivers State is located on latitudes between 4° 30'N and 5° 40'N and longitudes between 6° 25'E and 7° 33'E (Figure 1). Rivers State bounded on the south by the Atlantic Ocean, west by Bayelsa and Delta States, north by Imo, Abia and Anambra States and east by Akwa Ibom State. Rivers State has twenty-three local government areas presently. Geologically, the study area is underlain by the Coastal Plain sands having its place from the Pleistocenic Formation (Nwakoala and Warmate, 2014). The sediments are deposits comprising of gravel, clays, peats, sands and silt from the River Niger (Dekor, 2015). Rivers State is made up of both upland and riverine areas. The topography in the uplands ranges between 15 and 40m above the sea level while the mean elevation of about 15m is found in the riverine areas (Google Earth, 2013). The study which is situated in the Niger Delta region has a relatively flat terrain with marked absence of hills that rise above the general land surface (Albert, 2002). The study area enjoys a tropical climate with a mean temperature of 30°C and a relative humidity of 80% - 100%, and a mean yearly rainfall of about 2,300mm. The rainfall is always high but varies with seasons (Mmom and Fred-Nwagwu, 2013). Tropical rainforest is found in the hinterland part of Rivers State and mangrove swamps towards the coast the Atlantic Ocean. The vegetation represents the most luxuriant, the most complex, and the most diverse terrestrial ecosystem the world has known (Ojeh, 2011). The tropical rainforest vegetation comprises the moist evergreen plant species which are rich timber, palm trees, as well as fruit trees. The vegetation is nourished with high rainfall and high temperature, which provide favourable condition for the growth of a varieties of tall and big trees like mahogany, Obeche, Afara and abundance of oil palm trees and several other species of economically valuable plants such as raffia palms, Abura, ferns and grasses (Eludoyin et al., 2013). Rivers State is made up of silty-clay soil (Etu-Efeotor and Akpokodje, 1990). Freshwater loams and sandy loams, fluvial marine sediments and mangrove swamp alluvial soils made up the three major groups of soil in Rivers State (The Niger Delta Budget Monitoring Group (NDEBUMOG), 2007). The fluvial marine sediments comprise of coastal mud but texturally sandy. The major type of profession among the people of Rivers State is farming. In addition, fishing is another occupation widely practiced in the riverine areas of the state. This study focused on a simple random survey whereby it would be through collecting and analyzing data from only a small number of populace or items well thought-out to be representative of the entire group, and this strategy adopted by a researcher is to integrate the different components of a study in a coherent and logical way, it constitutes the blueprint for the collection and analysis of the collected data. The population of this study comprises the three (3) purposively selected Local government area in Rivers State and these

are Abua–Odual, Obio/Akpor and Eleme L.G.A. Five communities were randomly selected from each local government area namely; Abua/Odual - (Otari, omokwa, odaga, Omelema, Plans), Obio/Akpor - (Alakahia, Choba, Elenlewo, Rumuikini, Oroagbolu, Eleme - (Akpajo, Alesa, Onne, Aleto, Eteo). The formula for exponential growth model used for the projection is represented as thus;

$$P_n = P_o (1 + r)^n$$

Where;

P_o = Base Population

1 = Constant

r = Growth Rate (6.5%)

n = Number of year(s) to project the population (29 years: 1991 - 2020)

Sample size using the Taro Yamane Formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{(1 + N e)^2}$$

Where;

n = sample size

1 = constant

N = population size

e = sampling error (5%) = 0.0025

$$n = \frac{N}{(1 + N e)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{(1 + N e)^2}{152,386}$$

$$n = \frac{(1 + 152,386 (0.05))^2}{152,386}$$

$$n = \frac{(1 + 152,386 (0.0025))^2}{152,386}$$

$$n = \frac{(1 + N e)^2}{152,386}$$

$$n = \frac{1+380}{152,386}$$

$$\text{Sample size} = \frac{381}{152,386}$$

$$= 399$$

Primary and secondary data were initiated. The raw information is the primary data, it was gotten specifically from the researcher in the field work. The primary data is mainly through field survey/work with the help or use of research instruments as oral interview, personal observations and questionnaire administration to the dwellers/occupants in the settlement. Secondary data are those published Information or existing literature. These data were collected through the literature review process from sources such as journals magazines, reports of students publication of institution, previous research works, etc through these sources the researcher gathered data relevant to the objectives of this study. The instruments used in the research work in the collection of relevant data are checklist, observation, questionnaires and the personal interview. Structured questions that would ensure that the respondent does not divert from the response required by the researcher. The population sample was drawn with the aid of the random sampling techniques, The random sampling techniques is meant to be an unbiased representation of the total population by chosen randomly and it gives each sample an equal probability of being chosen. They are also some limitations in most research works which doesn't allow ghetto study of the entire population. A summary of respondent from the respondent was done using descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation. This is to aid

the analysis and enhance understanding and comprehension on the part of the public reading, the data so collected was presented in a tabular form. The method is chosen because of the simplicity and it is straight to the point.

Table 1 Sample Size Distribution and Population Projection

S/N	Local Government Area	1991 Population	Pop. Projection 2020 at 6.5%	No of Household	Sample Size
1	Abua Odual Community				
	Otari	3632	22554	3222	8
	Omokwa	94149	584665	83523	218
	Odaga	2718	16878	2411	6
	Omelema	7931	49251	7035	18
	Okana	3503	21766	3109	8
2	Obio Akpor Community				
	Alakahia	2402	14916	2130	5
	Choba	13766	85486	12212	31
	Elelenwo	4111	25529	3647	9
	Rumuekini	6376	39594	5656	14
	Oroalagbolu	3059	18996	2713	7
3	Eleme Community				
	Akpajo	6522	40501	5785	15
	Alesa	9423	58516	8359	21
	Onne	880	5464	780	2
	Aleto	8002	49692	7098	18
	Eteo	5305	32944	4706	12
	Grand Total			152,386	399

3. Results and discussion

This aspect of the study deals with research findings and analysis of data generated from the field through questionnaire distributions and retrieval. A total of three hundred and ninety-nine (399) questionnaires were administered to residents and three hundred and eighty (380) were retrieved, in different communities in the study areas.

3.1. Socio-economic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1 shows the sex distribution of respondents in the sample location which reveals that 67.1% of respondents are male with the highest percentage while 32.9% of the respondents are female with the lowest percentage. This indicates that there are more male than female in the sample location as at the time of this research. Table 2 shows the marital status of respondents in the study area and from all indications, 63.2% of respondents all across the communities are married, 28.9% of respondents across the communities are single, 6% of respondents across the communities of the respondents are widowed and 1.8% of the respondents across the communities are separated. Table 3 shows the age of respondents in the study area and it indicates that 40.7% of the respondents across all communities are between the age of 26 to 33 years, while 35.5% of the respondents across all communities are between the age of 34 to 41 years, 13.9% of the respondents in all the communities are between the age of 18 to 25 years and finally 9.7% of the respondents in all the communities are between the age 42 to 49 years. The analysis shows that the questionnaire were evenly distributed among the respondents in the study area. Table 4 shows that 47.4% of the respondents across all the communities have secondary education, 34.2% of the respondents across all the communities have primary education, 12.9% of the respondents across all the communities have tertiary education, 4.4% of the respondents across all the

communities have a vocational education while 1.1% of the respondents across all the communities have no formal education. Household size can be defined as the total number of people living under one roof and eating from one pot and by planning standards the minimum number of household in a rural settle is 7 and from the data gotten from the field and as presented in Table 5, 51.1% of the respondents in the study area have 7 to 8 household size, 41.8% of the respondents have 5 to 6 household size while 7.1% of the respondents have 3 to 4 household size. Figure 2 shows clearly that 51.1% of the respondents all across the communities are not employed, 36.6% of the respondents all across the communities are employed, 7.9% of the respondents all across the communities are house wives while 4.5% of the respondents all across the communities are retired. Table 6 shows that 50% of the respondents in all the communities in the study areas are traders, 28.9% of the respondents in all the communities are farmers, 8.9% of the respondents in all the communities are laborers, 6.6% of the respondents in all the communities are civil servants, 2.9% of the respondents in all the communities are technicians and 2.1% of the respondents in all the communities are artisans. Table 7 indicates that 43.4% of the respondents in the study area monthly income are within the range of ₦30,000 to ₦39,999 23.7% of the respondents monthly income are within the range of ₦19,000 - ₦29,999, 18.4% of respondents monthly income are within the range of ₦40,000 - ₦49,999 while 6.6% of the respondents monthly income are within the range of ₦50,000 - ₦59,999.

Figure 1 Sex Distribution of Respondents

Table 2 Marital status of respondents

S/No	Marital Status	Abua-Odual		Obio-Akpor		Eleme		Total	
		(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)
1	Single	35	35	45	28.1	30	25	110	28.9
2	Married	60	60	100	62.5	80	66.7	240	63.2
3	Widowed	5	5	12	7.5	6	5	23	6
4	Separated	0	0	3	1.8	4	3.3	7	1.8
5	Divorced	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Total	100	100	160	100	120	100	380	100

Table 3 Age of respondents

S/No	Age bracket	Abua-Odual		Obio-Akpor		Eleme		Total	
		(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)
1	18 – 25 years	28	28	15	9.3	10	8.3	53	13.9
2	26 – 33 years	45	45	60	37.5	50	41.7	155	40.7
3	34 – 41 years	25	25	70	43.7	40	33.3	135	35.5
4	42 – 49 years	2	2	15	9.3	20	16.7	37	9.7
5	50 years and above	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Total	100	100	160	100	120	100	380	100

Table 4 Educational level of respondents

S/No	Educational Level	Abua-Odual		Obio-Akpor		Eleme		Total	
		(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)
1	No formal education	2	2	1	0.6	1	0.6	4	1.1
2	Primary education	15	15	25	15.6	9	41.7	49	12.9
3	Secondary education	50	50	70	43.7	60	50	180	47.4
4	Tertiary education	30	30	60	37.5	40	33.3	130	34.2
5	Vocational education	3	3	4	2.5	10	8.3	17	4.4
	Total	100	100	160	100	120	100	380	100

Table 5 Household size of respondents

S/No	Household size	Abua- Odual		Obio-Akpor		Eleme		Total	
		(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)
1	Less than 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	3 to 4	2	2	16	10	9	7.5	27	7.1
3	5 to 6	45	45	64	40	50	41.7	159	41.8
4	7 to 8	53	53	80	50	61	50.8	194	51.1
5	9 and above	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Total	100	100	160	100	120	100	380	100

Figure 2 Employment status of respondents

Table 6 Occupation of respondent

S/No	Occupation of Respondents	Abua-Odual		Obio-Akpor		Eleme		Total	
		(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)
1	Farming	20	20	50	31.3	40	33.3	110	28.9
2	Trading	50	50	80	50	60	50	190	50
3	Civil Servant	10	10	10	6.3	5	4.2	25	6.6
4	Laborers	15	15	10	6.3	9	7.5	34	8.9
5	Technician	5	5	4	2.5	2	1.7	11	2.9
6	Artisan	0	0	4	2.5	4	3.3	8	2.1
	Total	100	100	160	100	120	100	380	100

Table 7 Monthly income category of respondents

S/No	Monthly income category	Abua-Odual		Obio-Akpor		Eleme		Total	
		(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)
1	Less than ₦8,000	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	₦8,000 - ₦18,000	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	₦19,000 - ₦29,999	30	30	40	25	20	16.7	90	23.7
4	₦30,000 - ₦39,999	45	45	60	37.5	60	50	165	43.4
5	₦40,000 - ₦49,999	25	25	40	25	15	12.5	70	18.4
6	₦50,000 - ₦59,999	0	0	20	12.5	5	4.2	25	6.6
7	₦60,000 and above	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Total	100	100	160	100	120	100	380	100

3.2. Quality of Services Provided By Social Infrastructures in the Study Area

Figure 3 Quality of services provided by social infrastructures in the study area

The social infrastructure in the study areas which are schools, health care centers, public conveniences, parks, etc., were analyzed in terms of quality of services that is to say how functional are the social infrastructures in the study area.

Figure 4 shows clearly that 48.7% of the respondents in all the communities in the study area said the quality of the services provided is fair, 25% of the respondents in all the communities in the study area said the quality of the services provided is bad, 21.8% of the respondents in all the selected communities said it is bad and 4.4% said it is very bad.

3.3. Major source of water available to your household

Table 8 shows that 48.7% of respondents in all communities in the study area main source of water is Borehole, 32.9% of respondents in all communities in the study area main source of water is well, 9.2% of the respondent in all communities in the study area main source of water is River/stream, 8.7% of the respondent in all communities in the study area main source of water is Pipeline water, while 1.5% of the respondents main source of water is rain.

Table 8 Major source of water available to your household

S/No	Major source of water	Abua-Odual		Obio-Akpor		Eleme		Total	
		(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)
1	Rivers / Stream	20	20	10	6.3	5	4.2	35	9.2
2	Borehole	45	45	80	50	60	50	185	48.7
3	Pipeline Water	5	5	8	5	20	16.7	33	8.7
4	Well	30	30	60	37.5	35	29.2	125	32.9
5	Rain	0	0	2	1.3	0	0	0	0
	Total	100	100	160	100	120	100	380	100

3.4. Means of Transportation By Your Household

Figure 4 shows that 76.6% of respondents in all the communities in the study area commute with Taxi/Buses, 15.8% of the respondents in all the communities in the study area commute with Motorcycle, 6.1% of respondents in all the communities in the study use Bicycle and 1.6% of the respondents in all the communities in the study area uses Truck.

Figure 4 Means of transportation by your household

3.5. Primary Source of Electricity

Table 9 shows that 81.6% of respondents in all the communities in the study area main source of electricity is PHCN – National grid, while 18.4% of respondents in all the communities main source of electricity is Private generator.

Table 9 Primary source of electricity

Source of Electricity	Abua-Odual		Obio-Akpor		Eleme		Total	
	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)
Private Generator	20	20	20	12.5	30	25	70	18.4
Community Generator	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
PHCN – National Grid	80	80	140	87.5	90	75	310	81.6
Total	100	100	160	100	120	100	380	100

3.6. Awareness of Any Physical Planning Authority

Figure 5 shows that 86.8% of the respondents in all communities in the study area said they are aware of the Physical Planning Authority while 13.2% of the respondents said no.

Figure 5 Aware of any Physical Planning Authority in the study areas

3.7. Availability of Facilities and Amenities in Your Community

Table 10 shows clearly the availability and functionality of the above facilities, all respondents in all the communities in the study area said agreed that the following facilities are available and functioning and those facilities are; Police post, Borehole, Pipe borne water, Market, Town Hall and School, 80% of the respondents in Abua-Odual community said that Hospital is available and functioning, 15% of the respondents in Abua-Odual community it is not available and 5% of the respondents in Abua-Odual community said it is available but not functioning. 83.3% of the respondents in Eleme community said that Hospital is available and functioning, 12.5% of the respondents in Eleme community it is available but not functioning and 4.2% of the respondents in Eleme community said it is not available. And all the respondents in Obio-Akpor said that Hospitals are available and functioning. All the respondents in Obio-Akpor and Eleme communities all agreed that Electricity is available and functioning. 70% of the respondents in Abua-Odual community said that Electricity is available and functioning; while 15% each of the respondents in Abua-Odual community said that the Electricity is available but not functioning and also not available. All the respondents in Obio-Akpor and Eleme communities all agreed that the tarred road is available and functioning. 80% of the respondents in Abua-Odual community said that the tarred road is available and functioning; while 20% of the respondents in Abua-Odual community said that there is no tarred road in the community. However, 85% of the respondents in Abua-Odual community said that Mono-Pump is not available, 10% of the respondents in Abua-Odual community said that Mono-Pump is available and 5% of the respondents in Abua-Odual community said that Mono-Pump is available but not functioning. 81.3% of the respondents in Obio-Akpor community said that Mono-pump is not available, 12.5% of the respondents in Obio-Akpor community said that Mono-pump is available and functioning while 6.3% of the respondents in Obio-Akpor community said that Mono-pump is available but not functioning. 83.3% of the respondents in Eleme community said that Mono-pump is not available, 8.3% each of Eleme respondents said that Mono-pump available and functioning and also available but not functioning.

Table 10 Available Facilities and Amenities

LGAs	Availability	School	Hospital	Market	Town Halls	Electricity	Pipe-Borne Water	Borehole	Tarred Road	Mono Pump	Police Post
Abua/Odual	Available	100	80	100	100	70	100	100	80	10	100
	Percentage (%)	100	80	100	100	70	100	100	80	10	100
	Not Available	0	15	0	0	15	0	0	20	85	0
	Percentage (%)	0	15	0	0	15	0	0	20	85	0
	Not Functioning	0	5	0	0	15	0	0	0	5	0
	Percentage (%)	0	5	0	0	15	0	0	0	5	0
Obio/Akpor	Available	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	20	160
	Percentage (%)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	12.5	100
	Not Available	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	130	0
	Percentage (%)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	81.3	0
	Not Functioning	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0
	Percentage (%)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.3	0
Eleme	Available	120	100	120	120	120	120	120	120	10	120
	Percentage (%)	100	83.3	100	100	100	100	100	100	8.3	100
	Not Available	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0
	Percentage (%)	0	4.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	83.3	0
	Not Functioning	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0
	Percentage (%)	0	12.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	8.3	0

3.8. Provision of Facilities and Amenities in Your Community

Table 11 shows clearly the provider of the above facilities and all respondents in the selected communities agreed that the government solely provides the facilities like School, Hospital, Electricity, Market, Police Post, Tarred roads and mono pump. All respondents in both Abua-Odual and Eleme communities agreed that it is the government that provides their town halls, in Obio-Akpor, 81.3% of the respondents said that it is the government that provides their town halls

while 18.7% of the respondents said that it is community effort. In Abua-Odual communities, 80% of the respondents said that is the government that provides Pipe-born water and bore hold facilities for them. In Obio-Akpor communities, 81.3% and 62.5% of the respondents said that it is the government that provides Pipe-born water and borehole, 9.4% and 12.5% of the respondents said that it is the community that provides pipe-born water and borehole; while 9.4% and 25% of the respondents said that it the Non-governmental Organization that provides Pipe-born water and borehole. In Eleme communities, 83.3% of the respondents said that the government provide Pipe-born water and Boreholes, 8.3% of the respondents said that it is the community effort and lastly, 8.3% of the respondents said that it is the Non-Governmental Organization that provides Pipe-born water and boreholes.

Table 11 Provider of the facilities and amenities in the community

S/N	Facilities / Amenities	Abua-Odual						Obio-Akpor						Eleme					
		Government		Community		Government		Community		Government		Community		Government		Community			
		(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)
1	School	100	100	0	0	0	0	160	100	0	0	0	0	120	100	0	0	0	0
2	Hospital	100	100	0	0	0	0	160	100	0	0	0	0	120	100	0	0	0	0
3	Market	100	100	0	0	0	0	160	100	0	0	0	0	120	100	0	0	0	0
4	Town Halls	100	100	0	0	0	0	130	81.3	30	18.7	0	0	120	100	0	0	0	0
5	Electricity	100	100	0	0	0	0	160	100	0	0	0	0	120	100	0	0	0	0
6	Pipe-Born Water	80	80	5	5	15	15	130	81.3	15	9.4	15	9.4	100	83.3	10	8.3	10	8.3
7	Borehole	80	80	5	5	15	15	100	62.5	20	12.5	40	25	100	83.3	10	8.3	10	8.3
8	Tarred Road	100	100	0	0	0	0	160	100	0	0	0	0	120	100	0	0	0	0
9	Mono Pump	100	100	0	0	0	0	160	100	0	0	0	0	120	100	0	0	0	0
10	Police Post	100	100	0	0	0	0	160	100	0	0	0	0	120	100	0	0	0	0

3.9. Respondents View on Effectiveness of the Physical Planning Authority in the LGAs

Table 12 Effectiveness of the Physical Planning Authority in the LGAs

S/No	Respondents View	Abua-Odual		Obio-Akpor		Eleme		Total	
		(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)
Do you take your building plan to the Physical Planning Authority in the LGA before commencement	Yes	80	80	120	75	100	83.3	300	78.9
	No	20	20	40	25	20	16.7	80	21.1
	Total	100	100	160	100	120	100	380	100
Reasons for saying NO	Not necessary	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Not aware	2	13.3	5	12.5	5	20	12	15
	Fees required	10	66.7	25	62.5	18	72	53	66.3
	They waste time to respond	3	20	8	20	2	8	13	16.3
	No reason	0	0	2	5	0	0	2	2.5
	Total	15	100	40	100	25	100	80	100

Table 12 shows that 78.9% of the respondents said that they take their building plan to the physical plan to the physical planning authority in the LGA before commencement of the project, while 21.1% of the respondents said they don't take

it the physical planning authority. Reasons for saying No was also given by the respondents in the study area and from the data gotten from field, 66.3% of the respondents in all the communities said that the reasons why they don't give their plan to physical planning authority is because the fees required are too much and too high, 16.3% of the respondents in all the communities said that the reason why they don't give their plan to physical planning authority is because they waste time to respond, 15% of the respondents in all the communities said that the reason why they don't give their plan to physical planning authority before commencement is because they are not aware and 2.5% of the respondents said no reason.

3.10. Availability of these Resources in the Community

Table 13 shows clearly that in all the communities under review, 80% of Abua-Odual respondents, 87.5% of Obio-Akpor respondents and 83.3% of Eleme respondents said that there is Oil and Gas in their communities, while 20% of Abua-Odual respondents, 12.5% of Obio-Akpor respondents and 16.7% of Eleme respondents said that there is no Oil and Gas in their communities. 70% of Abua-Odual respondents, 87.5% of Obio-Akpor respondents and 66.7% of Eleme respondents said that there is no sacred forest in their communities while 30% of Abua-Odual respondents, 12.5% of Obio-Akpor respondents and 33.3% of Eleme respondents said that there is sacred forest in their communities. All the respondents in the study area said that there is no water fall in the study area. 80% of Abua-Odual respondents, 93.8% of Obio-Akpor respondents and 95.8% of Eleme respondents said that there is land in the different communities while 20% of Abua-Odual respondents, 6.3% of Obio-Akpor respondents and 4.2% of Eleme respondents said that there is no land in their communities. 85% of Abua-Odual respondents, 12.5% of Obio-Akpor respondents and 83.3% of Eleme respondents said that there is large body of water while 15% of Abua-Odual respondents, 87.5% of Obio-Akpor respondents and 16.7% of Eleme respondents said that there is no large body of water in their communities.

Table 13 Availability of Resources in the Community

Respondents View	Response	Abua-Odual		Obio-Akpor		Eleme		Total	
		(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)	(N)	(%)
Oil and Gas in the community	Yes	80	80	140	87.5	100	83.3	320	84.2
	No	20	20	20	12.5	20	16.7	60	15.8
	Total	100	100	160	100	120	100	380	100
Sacred Forest	Yes	30	30	20	12.5	40	33.3	90	23.7
	No	70	70	140	87.5	80	66.7	290	76.3
	Total	100	100	160	100	120	100	380	100
Land	Yes	80	80	150	93.8	115	95.6	345	90.7
	No	20	20	10	6.2	5	4.4	35	9.3
	Total	100	100	160	100	120	100	380	100
Waterfall	Yes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	No	100	100	160	100	120	100	380	100
	Total	100	100	160	100	120	100	380	100
Large body of water	Yes	85	85	20	12.5	100	83.3	205	53.9
	No	15	15	140	87.5	20	16.7	175	46.1
	Total	100	100	160	100	120	100	380	100

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

It can be concluded that the available source of electricity is PHCN –National Grid. The available facilities are Police post, Borehole, Pipe borne water, Market, Town Hall and School in the entire study area. The major provider of the facilities and amenities is the government. The available resources are oil and gas, land and large body of water. Majority refused to take their building plan to the physical planning because of the fees required. It is therefore recommended that the state and local government joint account should be stopped and gives local government autonomy and full responsibility for their own share of federal fund allocation; international agencies who want to invest in projects that have direct bearing on the life of rural people should have direct access to those communities; self-help project should be encouraged among the rural communities by both the federal and state government; though joint account between state

and local government should be discouraged, but the state government must make it mandatory upon itself to monitor the spending of the local governments; only projects that have direct bearing onto the life of rural communities should be the priority; youth and women organization must be involved in the programme of rural development; and vital knowledge should be given to the type and the consequences of the various decision making mechanisms.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

We want to express our gratitude to the Reviewers for their hardworking attitudes and to the respondents of the study area.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

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